

Studies on the Thermodynamics of Adsorption in Clays : Nickel Adsorption on Na-, Ca- and Mg-Montmorillonites

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Equilibrium studies of the adsorption of Ni(II) on Na-, Ca- and Mg-saturated montmorillonites (pH 6.3 to 6.5) have been made. The data obey the Freundlich equation and follow the 'L' type of isotherm as defined by Giles *et al.* The thermodynamic parameters K_0 and ΔG_0 point out the higher affinity of Ni(II) on montmorillonite. The reaction was exothermic indicating the stronger binding of Ni(II) to clay surface. Results of thermodynamic study suggest an ion exchange process involving interdiffusion of ion in the exchange particle or in the film or a direct metal surface oxygen interaction. This view is further supported by the adsorption rate constant values, derived from rates of adsorption of Ni(II) on montmorillonites and isosteric heat of adsorption.

DURING the last decade a good deal of work has been done by scientists in different disciplines to develop preventive treatments for use in the control of crop pests. One of the most successful preventive treatments involves routine soil application of plant systematic insecticides¹. Clay minerals play a significant role in mobility and retention of inorganic and organic pesticide in soil, by virtue of the fact that the pesticides (particularly inorganic) associate with the oxide coatings of aluminosilicate clay minerals^{2,3}.

Numerous mechanism by which the inorganic pesticides may be adsorbed by oxides have been proposed⁴. Observations have shown that there is a relationship between metal cation adsorption and the cation hydrolysable property. Many workers^{5,6} have suggested that the mechanism of adsorption involves a direct metal surface oxygen interaction rather than non-specific electrostatic attraction between hydrolysable cation and negative charge clay surface. Nickel is an important trace element in plant nutrition and its formulations as NiCl₂ are also often used as fungicide⁷. In order to elucidate the mechanism of adsorption of nickel on montmorillonite, the present study was designed to investigate the adsorption of Ni(II) on Na-, Ca- and Mg-montmorillonites using the theoretical approaches of Van Bladel and Moreale^{8,9} and Bansal *et al.*¹⁰.

Experimental

The bentonite used in these studies was obtained from Akli in Rajasthan (India). Less than 2 μ m fraction was purified by sedimentation and centrifugation. X-ray diffraction revealed that the main constituent of the bentonite was montmorillonite. The suspension was converted into chloride free sodium ion saturated montmorillonite by Aldrich and Buchanan's method¹¹ by treating the clay suspension with 1N NaCl and 0.1N HCl. Calcium and magnesium saturated montmorillonites were prepared from sodium form by treating with CaCl₂

and MgCl₂ respectively using ion exchange technique. The pH of the clay-water suspensions was 6.3 to 6.5. The clay-water suspensions were used for experiments immediately after preparation. The concentration of all the clay-water suspensions varied from 9.26 to 11.24 g/l. The cation exchange capacity (CEC) determined by Jackson's¹² method was 740 μ eq/g clay. The surface area of the clay determined by ethylene glycol monoethyl ether method¹³ was 660, 640, 625 m²/g for Na-, Ca- and Mg-montmorillonites respectively.

Adsorption experiments were conducted by taking 10 ml of the appropriate montmorillonite suspension (pH 6.3 to 6.5) in a number of glass stoppered test-tubes and adding various amounts (0 to 15 ml) of standard NiCl₂ (0.01 N) and making up the volume to 25 ml with distilled water. The suspensions were shaken for 3 hr in a thermostat at constant temperature (21 $\pm$ 0.2, 31 $\pm$ 0.2, 41 $\pm$ 0.5 $^\circ$). Preliminary kinetic studies indicated that equilibrium was attained within 2 $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. Removal from the thermostat was followed by centrifugation, the samples being kept at the same temperature as during the experiment. The supernatant liquid was withdrawn for estimation of Ni(II). Nickel was estimated by titration with EDTA using copper-PAN indicator¹⁴. The amount of Ni(II) adsorbed was obtained from the amount of Ni(II) added minus Ni(II) remaining in the supernatants. All experiments were conducted in duplicate with reagent and clay blanks.

For the kinetic study, 10 ml of the appropriate clay-water suspension was added to 15 ml of standard nickel chloride solution in a number of glass stoppered test-tubes and shaken continuously at 21 $^\circ$. At appropriate time intervals tubes were removed, centrifuged and analysed for Ni(II) as mentioned above.

Results and Discussion

The nickel adsorption isotherm for Na-, Ca- and Mg-montmorillonites was best characterized by the

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linearized logarithmic form of the Freundlich equation :

$$\ln x/m = \ln K + 1/n \ln C$$

where $x/m = \mu\text{g}$ of nickel adsorbed per g clay, $C = \text{equilibrium nickel concentration } (\mu\text{g/ml})$, $1/n = \text{slope of log isotherm and log } K = \text{intercept at log } C = 0, C = 1 \mu\text{g/ml}$.

The constants K and $1/n$ provide rough estimates of the adsorbent capacity and the intensity of adsorption¹⁵. The values of the slope $1/n$ (Table 1)

TABLE 1—CONSTANTS FOR ADSORPTION CAPACITY OF Ni(II) ON Na-, Ca- AND Mg- MONTMORILLONITES AT 21, 31 AND 41°

Cation on clay	Temperature (°C)	Freundlich constants	
		$K(\pm S)^*$	$1/n(\pm S)^*$
Na-	21	470.2 ± 5.0	0.728 ± 0.003
	31	439.9 ± 3.7	0.711 ± 0.005
	41	422.9 ± 7.1	0.695 ± 0.003
Ca-	21	456.0 ± 1.3	0.718 ± 0.004
	31	431.3 ± 2.7	0.696 ± 0.004
	41	405.2 ± 7.0	0.684 ± 0.004
Mg-	21	407.8 ± 3.0	0.705 ± 0.005
	31	398.4 ± 4.0	0.681 ± 0.004
	41	391.4 ± 3.2	0.672 ± 0.003

* Standard error of estimate.

were in the order Na-> Ca-> Mg-montmorillonites and decreased with increase in temperature, indicating that the intensity of nickel adsorption was in the order Na-> Ca-> Mg-montmorillonites. The values of $1/n$ at all the three temperatures in all cases were less than unity, indicating a curvilinear type of isotherm. The curvilinear isotherm indicates an exponential decrease in the sorption energy as the proportion of adsorption sites saturated with Ni(II) became large¹⁶. The values of K (Freundlich constant) also confirm the earlier inferences on affinity of nickel on different forms of montmorillonite at all the three temperatures. Decrease in the K values with rise in temperature indicate the exothermic nature.

Adsorption of nickel on Na-, Ca- and Mg-saturated montmorillonite suspensions in the equilibrium concentration range 0 to 5 mM at 21, 31, 41° yielded isotherms as given in Fig. 1. An examination of adsorption isotherms revealed that they were similar to class 'L' as defined by Giles *et al*¹⁷. Such type of isotherms indicate that there was no strong competition from the solvent for adsorption sites and the adsorbed molecules were most probably adsorbed flat on the clay surface. The curvilinear response suggests that the number of available sites for adsorption becomes a limiting factor¹⁸. An examination of Fig. 1 showed that adsorption followed the order Na-> Ca-> Mg-montmorillonites and increase in temperature from 21 to 41° resulted in decrease of adsorption. This may be due to increased desorption by increasing the thermal energy of the adsorbate. Change in temperature only influences (Fig. 1) the number of adsorption site and affinity for nickel.

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherms of Ni(II) on Na-, Ca- and Mg-montmorillonites at 21, 31 and 41°. 1. ● Na-mont. 21°, 2. × Ca-mont. 21°, 3. ○ Mg-mont. 21°, 4. ▲ Na-mont. 31°, 5. △ Ca-mont. 31°, 6. ● Mg-mont. 31°, 7. □ Na-mont. 41°, 8. -○- Ca-mont. 41°, 9. -○- Mg-mont. 41°.

To obtain more insight into the mechanism(s) of the adsorption reaction, thermodynamic parameters at temperatures 21, 31, 41° were calculated from the variation of the thermodynamic equilibrium constant K_0 with change in temperature. The thermodynamic equilibrium constant K_0 for the adsorption of nickel was calculated from the relationship

$$K_0 = \frac{\gamma_s C_s}{\gamma_e C_e} = \frac{a_s}{a_e}$$

where a refers to the activity ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$); γ to the activity coefficient and C to the concentration of nickel ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). The subscripts s and e denote the adsorbent surface and the equilibrium solution respectively. The concentration of C_s (μg of solute adsorbed per ml of solvent in contact with adsorbent surface) was calculated from the relationship¹⁹ :

$$C_s = \frac{(\rho/M)A}{S_0/N(x/m)}$$

where $A = 1.091 \times 10^{-16} \left[\frac{M \times 10^{24}}{N\rho} \right]^{2/3}$, x/m is the amount adsorbed per unit of clay ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), ρ the density (g.ml^{-1}) of the solvent molecule, A the cross sectional area of the solvent molecule (cm^2/mole), M the molecular weight (g mole^{-1}) of the solvent molecule, N the Avogadro number and S_0 the surface area of the adsorbent ($\text{cm}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$). At infinite dilution

$$\lim_{\substack{C \rightarrow 0 \\ C_s \rightarrow 0}} \frac{a}{C} = 1$$

$$K_0 = \frac{a_s}{a_e} = \lim_{C_s \rightarrow 0} \frac{C_s}{C_e}$$

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR ADSORPTION OF Ni(II) ON Na-, Ca- AND Mg- MONTMORILLONITES AT 21, 31 AND 41°

Thermodynamic parameter	Na-montmorillonite			Ca-montmorillonite			Mg-montmorillonite		
	21	31	41	21	31	41	21	31	41°
Equilibrium constant (K_0)	1862	1396	1072	1445	1036	851.1	1365	1047	822.2
ΔG_0 (kJ/mole)	-18.46	-18.33	-18.25	-17.83	-17.74	-17.66	-17.70	-17.62	-17.52
ΔH_0 (kJ/mole)		-21.26 ± 0.20			-20.34 ± 0.18			-19.46 ± 0.24	
ΔS_0 (J/mole-degree)		-9.12 ± 0.04			-8.66 ± 0.04			-6.11 ± 0.07	

± Standard error of estimate.

The values of K_0 were obtained by plotting $\ln(C_s/C_e)$ vs C_s and extrapolating to $C_s=0$ vide Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. A plot of $\log(C_s/C_e)$ vs C_s .
 1. ● Na-mont. 21°,
 2. ▲ Ca-mont. 21°,
 3. ▲ Mg-mont. 21°,
 4. × Na-mont. 31°,
 5. ⊙ Ca-mont. 31°,
 6. ⊙ Mg-mont. 31°,
 7. ⊠ Na-mont. 41°,
 8. ⊠ Ca-mont. 41°,
 9. ⊠ Mg-mont. 41°.

An examination of Table 2 showed that the values of K_0 were always higher than unity, indicating that nickel had a high preference for montmorillonite surface. The value of K_0 confirms the deductions drawn from adsorption isotherm that adsorption of nickel on montmorillonite decreases with a rise in temperature and the order of adsorption is Na-mont. > Ca-mont. > Mg-mont.

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG_0), enthalpy (ΔH_0) and entropy (ΔS_0) were calculated from the relationships,

$$\Delta G_0 = -RT \ln K_0$$

$$\ln \frac{K_0 T_2}{K_0 T_1} = \frac{-\Delta H_0}{R} (1/T_2 - 1/T_1)$$

$$\Delta G_0 = \Delta H_0 - T \Delta S_0$$

The values are recorded in Table 2.

The values of ΔG_0 were negative at all the temperatures in all the cases and increased with a rise in temperature pointing towards the spontaneity of

the reaction with a higher preference for nickel to montmorillonites. Our earlier deductions drawn on the affinity of nickel for different forms of montmorillonite at all the three temperature stand confirmed by the values of ΔG_0 .

The values of ΔH_0 showed that the reaction is of exothermic nature, with a stronger binding of nickel ion to the clay surface. The values of ΔH_0 (Table 2) also confirmed our earlier deductions on the affinity of nickel for different forms of montmorillonite. The adsorption of nickel was accompanied by entropy loss. It may be due to changes in ion hydration as also reported elsewhere^{20, 21}.

At constant fractional coverage [$Q = (x/m)/q_0$] ($q_0 =$ maximum adsorption $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), the Clausius Clapeyron equation for dilute solutions permits the calculation of isosteric heat of adsorption as,

$$\Delta H_i = \frac{R(T_2 T_1)}{T_2 - T_1} \ln \frac{C_{e_1}}{C_{e_2}}$$

where C_{e_1} and C_{e_2} represent the equilibrium adsorbate concentrations in solution at a constant fractional coverage for temperature T_1 and T_2 respectively. The values of isosteric heat of adsorption of coverage (θ) 0 to 0.9 ranged from -16.3 to -2.5, -8.8 to -1.7 and 7.9 to 1.3 kJ/mole during Na-, Ca- and Mg-montmorillonites respectively. The low magnitude of ΔH_i ruled out the possibility of chemisorption. The most probable nature of adsorption was the physical type involving either an interdiffusion of an ion in the exchanger particle or in the film.

On the basis of the above results, it was concluded that Ni^{2+} ions on Na-, Ca- and Mg-montmorillonite surfaces (pH 6.3 to 6.5) can be adsorbed: (a) through coordination to the adsorbed hydroxyl ions at the edges of the clay²² and by sorption at negative sites on the mineral faces, and/or; (b) as a surface process in which Ni^{2+} is exchange for the H^+ ion chemically bound to the mineral surface as²³: $\text{MOH} + \text{Ni}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{M}-\text{O}-\text{Ni}^+ + \text{H}^+$; (c) or as a NiOH^+ ions, which possesses less hydration energy than Ni^{2+} ions as: $\text{MOH} + \text{NiOH}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{M}-\text{O}-\text{Ni}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}$; (d) or as a aquo nickel ion²⁴ on clay surface (where $\text{M} = \text{Na}^+, \text{Ca}^{2+}$ or Mg^{2+}).

Kinetic studies showed that the reaction was rapid initially and equilibrium was attained in 100 minutes. The rate constants for Na-, Ca- and Mg-montmorillonites being 3×10^{-4} , 2.55×10^{-4} and

$2.20 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ respectively. Such a result²⁵ support inference drawn from adsorption isotherm, heat of adsorption, isosteric heat of reaction viz. adsorption of Ni(II) on montmorillonite as an ion exchange process involving either an interdiffusion on an ion in the exchanger particle or in the film.

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